

EFFECT OF STUDY HABITS ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 11 STUDENTS IN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL MSU-SULU

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effect of study habits on academic performance of grade 11 students in senior high school MSU-Sulu year 2023-2024. Study habits is how certain individual learn. That is, the habits which the grade 11 students in senior high school learners form during their school years. Without good study habits, a learners on students cannot succeed. The adopted descriptive correlational method that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variable without making any claims about cause and effect. The researchers gathered 130 of grade 11 students in senior high school MSU-Sulu equally split between male and female. The survey questionnaire was applied in the study. The data analyzed and interpreted using SPSS computer program. Frequency and percentage weighted average mean (WAM), arithmetic mean, t-test, chi-square were use for analysis. Findings revealed that the level of there study habits were categorized as "Sometimes," suggesting room for improvement in consistency and dedication to studying and level of there academic performance was rated as "Very Satisfactory," reflecting commendable achievement. Also, revealed that there is no significant difference of study habits according to there demographic profile in terms of gender and strand. Moreover, the findings revealed that there is no significant relationship between study habits and the academic performance of students it means that the study habits of grade 11 students in senior high school MSU-Sulu in there academic performance will not be affected. The study concludes that these results can contribute

to the investigation of study habits on the academic performance and will guide future research.

Keywords: *study habits, academic performance, gender, strand, senior high school*

INTRODUCTION

Study habits can be defined as buying for out a devoted scheduled and un - uninterrupted time to follow oneself to the task of learning, practice, or enlightenment. Study habits are essential on the part of the students so that it can make use of their time successfully and purposely as an alternative of wasting time with insufficient learn about accomplishment. Study habits, according to Looyeh, et.al., (2017), study habits are patterns of study that students employ to comprehend and complete academic tasks. A student's daily routine at school includes developing study habits. It makes a major contribution to the growth of knowledge and ritualistic perception.

The researcher observed that grade 11 students at Mindanao State University-Sulu SHS, the researchers noticed that there was a range of study habits among grade 11 students. However, what remained unspoken was the impact of their habits inside the classroom before studying on their academic performance. Some students engaged in socializing or other activities during class breaks, which often resulted in a struggle to shift their focus to studying afterwards. These distractions affected their ability to concentrate and hindered their productivity, leading to potential challenges in achieving their desired academic outcomes. On the other hand, there were students who had the advantage of studying in advance. These proactive individuals managed to allocate time outside the classroom to review and prepare for upcoming lessons. Their advanced preparation allowed them to approach their studies with a clearer understanding, enabling them to excel academically. While not openly discussed, the constructing study habits and the presence or absence of pre-study distractions inside the classroom had varying effects on students` academic performance.

Despite the importance of study habits in academic success, there is a notable gap in the literature regarding the specific study habits that have the greatest impact on student performance. Further research is needed to identify and understand the most effective study habits that can optimize learning outcomes and address the influence of social media on study habits.

The goal of this study is to investigate the relationship between study habits and the academic performance of Grade 11 students in senior high school MSU-Sulu. It aims to identify the specific study habits that impact academic performance and understand the factors that hinder or enhance the development of affective study habits. The findings will provide insights for educators and policymakers to design interventions and strategies to improve study habits and enhance academic performance among Grade 11 students.

Research Questions

This study assessed the Effect of Study Habits on Academic Performance of Grade 11 Students in Senior High School MSU - Sulu.

Specifically, this paper answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender and strand?
2. What is the level study habits of grade 11 students at MSU - Sulu SHS?
3. What is the level of academic performance?
4. Is there a significant difference on the study habits of the students when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender and strand?
5. Is there a significant relationship between study habits and the academic performance of students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the MSU - Sulu Senior High School Department, which is located at Capitol Site, Jolo Sulu, near the provincial office of Sulu. The said department has two building: the main building can be found near the campus gymnasium, and the second building located between College of Agriculture and the College of Arts and Sciences. Furthermore, it offers two strand General Academic Strand (GAS) and Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM), headed by Dr. Norman Abdurahman.

Sampling Method

The participants of the study were 130 of grade 11 STEM and GAS students of Mindanao State University - Sulu Senior High School. Who are currently enrolled in the academic year 2023 - 2024, consisting of six (6) sections of Grade 11 STEM and seven (7) sections of grade 11 GAS. Ten (10) students or respondents handed each question.

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani et al. (2024), Jarak et. al. (2024), Sasapan et. al. (2024), Sakili et. al. (2024), Hadjibun et. al. (2024), and Sabbaha et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

The closed-ended survey questionnaire was one of the tools that the researchers

used to collect the data they needed for the study. The students in the senior high school department received the questionnaires with the prepared survey questions. These questionnaires used to determine the effect of poor study habits on academic performance of grade 11 students in Senior High School MSU - Sulu.

Data Gathering Procedure

During gathering the empirical data, the first step applied by the researchers was to ensure the permit from the director of Mindanao State University- Sulu Senior High School. After receiving the approved request from the director, they proceeded to the coordinator of Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and General Academic Strand (GAS) to hand over the coordinators can notify the advisers in their perspective strand.

Statistical Techniques

The researchers used Frequency and Percentage to identify the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender and strand, Weighted Average Mean used to determine the level of study habits of grade 11 students at MSU - Sulu SHS, Arithmetic Mean used to determine the level of academic of academic performance, T -test used to determine if there a significant different on the study habits of students when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender and strand, and Chi - Square used to determine if there a significant relationship between study habits and the academic performance of students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1

Demographic Profile of Respondents in terms of Gender		
Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	65	50.0%
Female	65	50.0%
Total	130	100%

The table shows that there were 65 male respondents, which accounts for 50% of the total respondents. Similarly, there were 65 female respondents, also making up 50% of the total. This indicates that the number of male and female respondents is equal. The total number of respondents recorded in the table is 130, which represents 100% of the total respondents.

Table 1.2

Demographic Profile of Respondents in terms of Strand		
Strand	Frequency	Percentage
STEM	60	46.2%
GAS	70	53.8%
Total	130	100%

The table shows that out of the total 130 respondents, 60 of them belong to the STEM strand, which represents 46.2% of the total respondents. On the other hand, 70 respondents belong to the GAS strand, accounting for 53.8% of the total. From this data, we can conclude that the majority of the respondents, with a percentage of 53.8%, are from the GAS strand. This suggests that there is a higher representation of respondents from the GAS field compared to the STEM field.

Table 2**Level of study habits of grade 11 students at MSU-Sulu SHS**

Statement	M	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
1. I look other references to further understand.	3.4	1.2	Sometimes
2. I have a specific place of study at home that I keep clean and orderly.	3.3	1.2	Sometimes
3. I take down notes during class discussion.	3.2	1.2	Sometimes
4. If I am absent from my class. I ask my classmate what I missed.	3.2	1.4	Sometimes
5. After the discussion of my teacher, I re-read my notes.	3.2	1.0	Sometimes
6. I regularly review my lesson after class discussion.	3.2	1.0	Sometimes
7. I discuss work assignments with other.	3.2	1.2	Sometimes
8. I ask my teachers about the topic that I cannot understand.	3.1	1.1	Sometimes
9. I prepare for discussion/recitation before my class.	3.1	1.1	Sometimes
10 I spend at least 3 hours studying each day/night.	3.0	1.0	Sometimes
Overall Mean	3.2	1.2	Sometimes

Legend: 1.00-1.79=Never, 1.80-2.59=Rarely, 2.60-3.39=Sometimes, 3.40-4.19=Always, 4.20-5.00=Often

The table shows the level of study habits of grade 11 students at MSU-Sulu SHS. The overall mean for all the statements is 3.19, SD= 1.2, indicating that the students' study habits are categorized as "Sometimes". This means that the students study habits suggests that there is room for improvement in terms of consistency and dedication to studying. It is important for the students to develop more regular study habits to enhance their learning and academic performance. The researcher suggest that no one knows what they are doing inside the classroom during exams or different activities, whether it is good or not what they are doing, such as cheating in class or if they have strategies they are implementing.

According to Rafiq Ahmad Lone (2021), study habits are the ways or patterns that a person uses to understand or comprehend the study content and achieve achievement. These are defined by how, when, and why people study. Study habits are the normal time devoted by a person to understand a topic or study for exams in order to seek a degree. Study habits are the numerous behavioral patterns used by people to prepare for tests or learn academic subjects. Good study habits are most important in promoting academic accomplishment. Study habits have a significant impact on a person's overall personality development, as well as their academic success.

Table 3

Level of Academic performance		
Academic Performance	Mean	Verbal Description
Grade 11 students	87.4	Very Satisfactory

Legend: Outstanding=90-100, Very Satisfactory=85-89, Satisfactory=80-84, Fairly Satisfactory=75-79, Did Not Meet the Expectation=74 or below.

The table presents the level of academic performance of Grade 11 students. The mean score for their academic performance is 87.43, which falls within the range of Very Satisfactory. Based on the legend provided, the verbal description for this range indicates that the student's academic performance is considered very satisfactory. This suggests that the students are performing well and meeting or exceeding expectations in their academic endeavors. It is important to note that academic performance can be influenced by various factors, including study habits, engagement in class, and individual abilities. The "Very Satisfactory" rating implies that the Grade 11 students are achieving a high level of performance and are on track academically. Overall, this result suggests that the students' academic performance is commendable and reflects their dedication and efforts in their studies.

Evans Austin et.al., (2021) stated, students who are above average academically and are positively exposed to these elements are more likely to perform well than those who are not exposed to them. The report suggests that aspects such as truancy, parental education, and income levels, textbook availability and accessibility, libraries, practical laboratories, lunch provision, and teachers be reviewed and altered on a regular basis to

satisfy students' needs and expectations. This will significantly improve students' academic performance and, as a result, their ability to attain their life goals.

Table 4.1
Significant Difference on the Study Habits of the Students when grouped according to their Demographic profile in terms of Gender.

Variable	Male	Female	t (128)	P- value
	M	M	-	.172
	SD	SD	7.375	
Gender	3.1	3.3		
	0.6	0.8		

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

An independent sample t-test was performed to compare the study habits between male and female respondents. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the study habits between male (M=3.1, SD=0.6) and female respondents (M=3.3, SD=0.8); $t(128), p = .172$.

According to Daniel, et al. (2014), This meta-analysis examines gender differences in scholastic achievement and finds that there is no significant difference in study habits between males and females.

Table 4.2
Significant Difference on the Study Habits of the Students when grouped according to their Demographic profile in terms of Strand.

Variable	STEM	GAS	t (128) P-value
	M	M	-1.815
	SD	SD	.072
Strand	3.1	3.3	
	0.8	0.7	

**Significant at $p < 0.05$*

An independent sample t-test was performed to compare the study habits between male and female respondents. The findings revealed that there is no significant difference in the study habits between STEM (M=3.1, SD=0.8) and GAS respondents (M=3.3, SD=0.7); $t(128), p = .172$. The table shows that the t-test results suggest that students in the STEM strand have lower study habits scores compared to students in the GAS strand based on the given data. However, it is important to note that further analysis and consideration of other factors may be necessary to fully understand the relationship between strand and study habits.

Table 7
Significant relationship between study habits and the academic performance of students

Parameters		Academic Performance				X ²	P
		Outstanding	Very Fairly	Satisfactory	Satisfactory		
Study Habits	Never	0	2	2	2	8.149	.771
	Rarely	0	4	9	2		
	Sometimes	1	4	33	12		
	Always	0	8	33	10		
	Often	0	1	5	2		

Note. X² = Chi-square value

*Significant at p<0.05

A Chi-Square test of Association was performed to assess the relationship between Academic performance and study habits. The findings revealed that there was no significant relationship between the two variable, $\chi^2 = 8.149$, p-.771. The data collected doesn't provide enough evidence to conclude that the study habits have a significant impact in which academic performance of respondents.

This means that students academic performance is not determined by their study habits. Indicating that a students level of academic achievement is not strongly dependent on their study habits alone. While study habits are often considered an important factor in academic success, the findings imply that other elements, such as individual abilities, motivation, teaching methods, and socioeconomic factors, may play a more crucial role in shaping a students performance. This suggests that a more holistic approach to understanding and supporting student success is necessary, considering a wide range of factors beyond just study habits.

Study by Tus, et.al., (2020), Academic performance and study habits had no significant relationship, according to the results. The findings additionally demonstrated that the pupils' study habits are comparatively average. Developing students' study habits is also important for boosting their academic performance, particularly with regard to note-taking, reading comprehension, and overall wellness. According to Lawrence's (2014), study reveals that the researcher looked into the possible correlation between higher secondary school students' academic performance and their study habits. The results of his investigation showed that the variables included in the study have no significant differences from one another. The data suggests that the frequency of study does not significantly affect the academic performance of students. However, it should be noted that these results are specific to this sample and may not be representative of all students. Further research is needed to explore this relationship in a larger population.

Conclusions

The study conducted on the effect of study habits on academic performance of Grade 11 students in senior high school at MSU-Sulu the researchers indicate, based on the study findings, an equal distribution of male and female respondents, with 50% each, totaling 130 respondents. The majority, 53.8%, belong to the GAS strand, suggesting a higher representation in this field compared to STEM. The study habits of Grade 11 students at MSU-Sulu SHS are categorized as "Sometimes," indicating room for improvement in consistency and dedication to studying. While the academic performance of Grade 11 students is very satisfactory, with a mean score of 87.43, suggesting that students are performing well and meeting or exceeding expectations academically, Statistical analysis showed no significant difference in study habits between male and female respondents, as well as between STEM and GAS respondents, and the Chi-Square test revealed no significant relationship between academic performance and study habits, implying that academic achievement is not solely dependent on study habits. Other factors, like individual abilities, motivation, teaching methods, and socioeconomic factors, may play a more significant role in shaping student performance. Study habits are important, and the findings suggest that a holistic approach considering various factors beyond study habits is crucial in understanding and supporting student success effectively. Individual abilities, motivation, and external factors also play a vital role in shaping students' academic performance. Therefore, a comprehensive approach that addresses multiple aspects of student development is essential for fostering academic success.

Recommendations

In line with the findings, gap and conclusion, the researchers recommend the following courses; The researchers opinion to students who do not prioritize studying are missing out on valuable opportunities for growth and academic success. Studying is not just about memorizing facts and information; it is a process that allows students to deepen their understanding, develop critical thinking skills, and make meaningful connections between concepts. By neglecting to study, students may struggle to grasp complex topics, retain information, and perform well on assessments. Moreover, consistent and effective studying helps students build discipline, time management skills, and a strong work ethic that can benefit them beyond the classroom. It is important for students to recognize the long-term benefits of studying and cultivate a mindset that values continuous learning and personal growth.

To students, developing good study habits is crucial for academic success. It is recommended that students create a regular study schedule and allocate at least 3 hours each day for studying. Creating a conducive study environment at home, free from distractions, can also help improve focus and concentration. Reviewing lessons after class discussions and seeking clarification from teachers when needed are important study habits. Preparing for discussions and recitations in advance, taking down notes during class, and collaborating with classmates for work assignments can enhance

understanding and retention of information. Additionally, utilizing additional references and staying focused during study time are key study habits that can contribute to improved academic performance.

To parents, it is important to support and encourage your children in developing good study habits. Providing a quiet and organized study space at home can help create a conducive environment for studying. It is also important to monitor your children's study schedule and progress and communicate with their teachers to stay updated on their academic performance. Encouraging reading habits and providing access to books and other reading materials can further enhance their learning. Promoting a balanced lifestyle that includes sufficient rest, exercise, and recreation is also important for their overall well-being and academic success.

To teachers play a crucial role in promoting good study habits among students. Emphasizing the importance of effective studying and providing guidance and resources can help students develop these habits. Encouraging active participation and engagement in class discussions, offering additional support and clarification when needed, and providing opportunities for collaborative learning can enhance students' understanding and retention of information. Giving regular feedback and assessments can help students track their progress and identify areas for improvement. Creating a positive and conducive learning environment is also essential in fostering good study habits among students. Additionally, teachers can scaffold learning, teach study skills explicitly, and foster self-regulation and metacognition. Utilizing technology tools, fostering a growth mindset culture, and collaborating with parents and guardians can further enhance the promotion of good study habits. By implementing these strategies, teachers can empower students to become independent learners and achieve academic success.

To administrators, allocating resources for creating conducive study environments in schools, such as quiet study areas and access to learning materials, can also contribute to the development of good study habits. Implementing policies and programs that support and encourage these habits, as well as collaborating with parents and teachers to monitor and support students' study habits and academic performance, are important steps in fostering a culture of effective studying within the school community.

To the future researchers, should cultivate a strong sense of curiosity and a desire for lifelong learning. They should be open-minded, willing to question established theories and explore new ideas. Developing interventions and strategies to improve study habits and enhance academic performance can further contribute to the field of education. Considering demographic profiles, such as gender and strand, in relation to study habits and academic performance can also provide valuable insights for future research.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Researchers have guaranteed that participants in the study will have the freedom to check and respond to the questionnaire provided. Furthermore, the researchers ensure that the questionnaire is readable. and concise.

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